

The Power of Graphic Design in Promoting Tourism In Ghana

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ABSTRACT: *The study focused on bringing to light various graphic design elements that can be used to accelerate the development of the Ghanaian tourism industry. Even though Ghana has a lot of tourist sites scattered across the country, its tourism potential has not been harnessed to the fullest. This stems from the fact that the method of publicity is far below expectation. Most of the places do not even have signage to advertise them to both the local Ghanaian citizens let alone foreigners who crave to visit places of interest. The few that have signage, the signage have outlived their usefulness as they stand at the mercy of the weather. However, in modern-day advertising, several mediums are available to make effective communication yet the various tourist sites seem oblivious about this and are not taking advantage of them to catch the attention of prospective visitors. To bring this to the fore, the study employed the descriptive research approach as it aimed at re-echoing the availability and the use of graphic design products as effective promotional materials to propel the tourism business in Ghana forward. This was made possible by collecting data related to the use of various graphic design media that can help the tourism industry players to boost the industries' activities in order to be recognized among the major tourism destinations in Africa and the world at large. The data which consisted of primary and secondary data enabled the description of the situation to be more vivid as possible. The Study revealed that graphic design elements such as powerful and elegant logos, brilliant brochure designs, attractive websites, and the internet, posting elegant pictures on Social media, and infographics are some of the graphics that could be used.*

KEYWORDS - *graphic design, graphics, graphic design elements, tourism, tourism industry*

I. INTRODUCTION

Graphic design, according to Jamology (2022) is “the art and practice of planning and projecting ideas and experiences with visual and textual content.” It is a medium of communication that uses various ideas or messages in a visual way. These visuals are depicted in the form of illustrations, business logos, Photographs, typography, page layouts on a website or motion graphics. This is made possible by creating combinations of these elements into appealing images that are used to help boost business in several ways by way of capturing people’s attention, selling products and services, and opening new markets as well. The use of graphic design has been an integral part of human life and it is associated with almost all the day-to-day activities of people all over the world. It is the graphic designer who creates a design for usability and effective communication of information or ideas. In order to achieve the desired communication result, the designer designs and produces a magazine layout, a website, a user experience, a project flow, or other things that require overall consideration in order to achieve the best accessibility possible.

In entertainment, design plays an instrumental role in creating the graphic pieces outlined in the script. In a TV or film production, the graphic designers are responsible for the creation of promotional materials, such as movie posters and digital content; develop a unique look and feel for the production; and essentially, do their part to create a whole new world in which the story can unfold. They move the plot forward, and create a compelling atmosphere through expertly designed visual elements. Most of the time, graphic designers work on period pieces (set in the past), which require a lot of research to imitate the exact style and presentation of things

including building signage and newspapers. For these reasons, Herzing Blog (2021) declare that “from product packaging to newspapers to background signs to personal notes: every element of graphic design must be carefully considered in TV and film” In business, graphic design is used as a powerful marketing tool in promoting sales and services by communicating the unique brand story to your current and future customers. The application of simple design choices such as fonts and impressive color schemes become a driving force help deliver business messages with both feeling and clarity in such a way that supports the brand message.

Design trends evolve and change with time as in the case of graphic design. That is why it is used in every form of communication including newspapers, magazines, websites, and apps. Graphic design is used to influence people because, in our lives, it is sometimes more noticeable than obvious more (Staff, 2022). How graphic design impact peoples’ behaviour cannot be overemphasized in the sense that the way people use logos, fonts, or colours, illustrations affect their behaviour and shows how design influences their decisions and even their emotions.

In business and commercial activities, Graphic Design offers a broad range of uses including the use various graphic design elements to communicate with their customers. Some of these graphics are also used in advertisements to sell their products or services and to attract and keep customers. These may include the use of text, displays, icons, illustrations or images, etc. businesses use graphic design to inspire and make the customer feel special. These and many more benefits of using graphic design in business and professions make consumers build brand loyalty which in turn promotes and move the business to the next level. In so doing, there is a boost in the income levels of the business and the ultimate aim of maximizing profit is achieved.

However, the tourism sector of Ghana’s economy has not exploited these overwhelming benefits to its advantage to boost and attract a lot of visitors even though Ghana has numerous tourist sites scattered across the length and breadth of the country. As people both citizens and foreigners travel along the roads to their destinations, it is hard to locate impressive signage of tourist sites. The story is not different from the situation in the cities, towns, and the Metropolises. Few of the tourist sites that have signboards, they are outmoded, defaced, and outlived their usefulness.

II. METHODOLOGY

The study employed the descriptive research approach as it aimed at throwing light on promotional issues in the tourism industry in Ghana. This was made possible by collecting data related to the use of various graphic design media that can help the tourism industry players to boost the industries activities in order to be recognized among the major tourism destinations in Africa and the world at large. The data which consisted of primary and secondary data enabled the description of the situation to be more vivid as possible. The choice of descriptive method was necessitated by the fact that the study sought to describe various aspects of the phenomenon that can help the tourism industry in Ghana to thrive. In the process, it was used to describe the characteristics of identified graphic design elements (media) to be used by the industry and did not focus on reasons for the occurrence of the phenomenon. It made it possible for the observation of the phenomenon in the tourism industry to be observed in a completely natural and unchanged natural environment.

III. DISCUSSION

3.1 Definitions of Graphic Design

Bertoline, Wiebe, Muller and Nasman (1995) claim that graphics is a Visual communication language incorporating text, image and numeric information. Graphics include everything from the more traditional types of engineering drawings to sophisticated computer models, such as the solid mechanical part or the display in the goggles of a virtual reality system which follow the rules or laws of visual science. According to the Oxford Dictionary of Art (1988), the term “Graphic Art” (graphic design) has several meanings but in the context of the fine arts, it most usually refers to the arts that depend mostly on line or tone instead of colour. From this definition, graphic art can be considered as involving drawing and engraving since the most essential elements

needed are lines. The Oxford Dictionary of Art further explains the term as being used to cover the entire field of commercial printing including text and illustration.

On its part, the World Book Encyclopaedia (1985) describes graphic art as a general term for drawing and other techniques used to reproduce words and pictures. This technique includes block printing, engraving, etching, lithography, and silk screen printing. It further describes graphics as being used commercially to advertise, prepare newspapers, magazines, illustrations as well as pamphlets, art production, bookbinding, and fashion design and lithography. Graphic design is a creative medium in which designers communicate ideas or information through visual organization and design. It serves as a bridge between a product or service, and the consumer of a product or service.

Graphic Design is defined as the visual design of content in which design style is described by functionality and basic symbolism. Graphic design is useful in numerous forms of media. Apart from the traditional print media such as magazines, books, and posters, graphic design is also used in electronic and interactive media. The combination of words, symbols, and images is done by the use of various artistic and technical means to convey information to viewers. Consequently, it is also referred to as visual communication or communication design. Graphic design is very often linked closely to current events and diverse cultural influences in society. Its range of applications consists of advertisement, branding, public relations, and communication for science and culture. Due to the availability of a wide range of applications, it is essential for any graphic designer to have a greater understanding of typography, visual arts, and layout (Machine, 2022).

From the definitions so far, it can be deduced that Graphic design is a process of working with lettering, lines, illustration, or images to make representations for understandable visual communication. It can also be said to include the production of postage stamps, trademarks, billboards, and television commercials (advertisements), the designing of brochures, packages, posters, and the printing of books and magazines. Etching, engraving, block printing as well as other forms of printing such as silkscreen printing are all works of graphics. Graphic design is one of the most important aspects of our lives that is seen everywhere ranging from the adverts on Television to the posters that are seen along the ways. Graphic design is used to convey messages, sell products, and create an overall image for a company or organization” (Graphic Elements, 2022).

3.2 Types of Graphic Design

There are many different forms of graphic design. The most common ones are:

- Product Design/User Experience (UX) design. When working in UX design, graphic designers challenge themselves with making a website, application, or other technologically-based media as simple as possible to the satisfaction of the consumers who use it.
- Website design, which requires graphic designers to employ colors, textures, layout, icons, and more to make the websites user-friendly and informative as much as possible.
- Branding or visual identity design. This encompasses the creation of recognizable visuals for products or services in such a way that materials from those products and services are used to attract the attention of both former and new clients and broaden their overall reach.
- Publication design, in which the graphic designer focuses on the appearance, organization, and accessibility of published materials such as books, magazines, etc.
- Packaging design, which involves the development of packaging for various products in line with a producer’s budget, preferred visual effects, desired materials etc. and more determined to create an attractive package to meeting a product's expectations.

3.3 Importance of Graphic Design

del Rosario (2022) points out that “While a picture may be worth a thousand words, graphic design can be worth thousands of dollars in any business. Graphic design is more than just aesthetics. It is a form of communication link for businesses and the audience. Businesses use graphics in every stage of the marketing process to inform, engage, and eventually influence prospective customers to make purchasing decision or take a desired action”

Graphic design is an artistic medium that communicates ideas and messages through visuals and text. Although it is most commonly connected with marketing and advertising, graphic design can be found throughout our day-to-day life. Conklin and Kennedy (2022) cite examples of the importance of Graphic design to include the straightforward usability and helpful graphics on a patient portal a client might use in order to communicate with their doctor's office; drawing new customers in to make purchases at a new coffee shop' with posters, logo, takeaway cups, bags, and napkins which stand out as unique and interesting. They further state that Graphic design helps make a math textbook as clear, easy-to-use, and interesting as possible, thanks to graphics and text arrangement, and the use of colour. In sum, graphic design is used in across many different facets of human life, making messages and ideas more interesting, accessible, or otherwise useful in daily life (Conklin & Kennedy, 2022).

From the point of view of Jof (2021) Graphic design is important to businesses and our everyday lives in many ways saying that “We come across with logos, brochures, websites and host of other design products daily. Packaging, branding, signage, books, magazines, etc. are typical examples of the use of a wide variety of graphic designs”. The Community derived so many benefits from graphic design to spread awareness of community needs. The use of graphic design helps to give a unique approach to understanding the community with visual images that could be understood by both literates and non-literates. This able to encourage people to contribute and give of their time and other resources to the benefit/ development of the community. The use of graphics shows people that a community is used to make the world become a better place to live in.

Discussing the importance of graphics may not be complete without talking about the benefits of using Graphic Design in Education. The designing of textbooks helps in no small measure to improve the cognitive development and language skills of children; helps children to learn visual literacy, literacy, art, and design, making it imperative for parents to use graphic design to teach their children for the utmost comprehension. Furthermore, schools use graphic design to improve their performance in the assessment system. Data presentation and the structure of the data are normally enhanced by graphics. Graphic design controls the viewers' ability to receive important messages by means of an artwork. It has a significant effect on how society functions daily. Graphic design has changed so many features of how society used to be in the past, and it is still developing in the present. The impact/impart of graphic design affects lives in many positive ways such that its application in tourism will be an enhancement in the Ghanaian tourism industry.

3.4 Definitions of Tourism

Tourism is an activity of recreation that tourists go for at long-distance sightseeing. The folk culture, local conditions and customs, social customs, and so on of tourist areas will bring tourists novelty to the vision, stimulating their visual perception and arousing their aesthetic potentials (Guohua, 2015). Walton (2022) also defines tourism as ‘the act and process of spending time away from home in pursuit of recreation, relaxation, and pleasure, while making use of the commercial provision of services. Tourism fundamentally means the activities embark on by visitors. The tourism industry comprises all activity that takes place in the visitor economy. It consists of activities directly related to the tourist, such as visiting a tourist attraction, staying in a hotel, or ordering a meal. It also involves indirect activities like the transport company that delivers the food to the restaurant in which the tourist eats or the laundry company that is engaged by the hotel to clean bed sheets.

Macintosh and Goeldner (2010) state that “the definition of tourism varies from one source to the other, person to person and there is no consensus concerning the definition of tourism. Nearly every institution defines “tourism” differently. But when it comes to explaining it with the basic terms, it can be summed up as follows:

Tourism consists of a number of activities, services, and industries that provide travel experiences including accommodation, transportation, entertainment businesses, eating and drinking establishments, retail shops, and other hospitality services for individuals or groups who have travelled away from home. It constitutes the total

occurrences and relationships that arise from the interaction of tourists, business suppliers, host communities and the host governments in the process of attracting and hosting these tourists and other visitors”

There are many diverse shapes and sizes when it comes to tourism and there are various types of tourism. These include niche tourism mass tourism and special interest tourism. There is domestic tourism and international tourism which could be either inbound tourism or outbound tourism. The range of different forms of tourism notwithstanding, all of them come under a broad tourism umbrella because they all deal with visitors and feed the visitor economy in one way or the other.

Tourism is an occurrence without any universal definition due to the complex nature and the individualism of the travellers themselves and the activities they opt to undertake. However, the most widely used definition of tourism is the one by the World Trade Organisation (WTO) and United Nations (UN) Statistics Division (1994), which proposes that the qualification as a tourist is that people must travel and stay in a place outside of their normal residential environment for a period not more than one consecutive year for leisure, business or other purposes. Conversely, Mathieson and Wall (1982) on their part, opine that there should not be any imposition of a timeframe in tourism, they simply state that “one must travel to a destination temporarily”.

Leiper (1979) also subscribes to the fact that defining tourism is more complex and proposes three approaches that have to be taken into consideration in order to define tourism. These are: looking at it from the economic standpoint that focuses on tourism as a business; the technical position that concentrates on the tourist in order to offer a common foundation by which to collect data and the holistic posture that attempts to include the whole essence of the subject.

Macintosh and Goeldner (2010) declare that “Tourism is different from travel and for tourism to happen, there must be a displacement: an individual has to travel, through any means of transportation”. Nevertheless, all travel cannot be said to be tourism, and that three criteria have to be used concurrently in order to describe a trip fit to be described as tourism. The displacement be that;

- involves displacement of the tourist outside the usual environment
- the travel must occur for any purpose different other than being a remuneration from within the place visited: the previous limits, where tourism was restricted to recreation, visiting family and friends but has now been expanded to include a vast array of purposes;
- Only the maximal duration is declared and not the minimal. Tourism displacement can be with or without staying overnight. (Macintosh & Goeldner, 2010)

3.5 Importance of Tourism

The popularity of “Rural tourism” has increased dramatically because tourists from busy cities crave for more natural environments. For that reason, they seek unique experiences like staying on a farm, going on hiking for days with guides, doing rock climbing, and more. The result of these visits is the jobs they create for people living in these rural areas and make authorities become aware that these places are worth preserving and investing in. It also offers opportunities for tourists to get first-hand knowledge about the areas in their natural setting while they form a closer connection with the people who live there (TheImportantSite, 2022).

Galinsky is quoted in TheImportantSite (2022) as saying that “experiences in other countries can increase a person’s cognitive flexibility, though it depends on how a person engages”. Travelling also boosts peoples’ happiness and brings down their stress. Only a few people can afford a luxury travel experience, however, visits to local cultural sites and natural areas can also benefit the well-being of a person. Tourism contributes to the complete growth and development of a country by bringing numerous economic value and benefits as well as helping in the building of the country’s brand value, image, and identity. The tourism industry goes beyond attractive destinations, to being an important economic growth contributor (Thakur, 2018). Tourism brings people from everywhere in the world and such, connects people with places, people with people, and places with places.

3.6 Tourism in Ghana

Ghana is regarded as one of the peaceful and stable countries in the world, is a small beautiful cultural-filled country situated in West Africa with impressive tourist sites to show the world. Ghana has vast sunny beaches, lively cities, historical sites, friendly people, and easy methods of travelling around the country. This makes Ghana a great place to visit for tourists (Caeser, 2022).

There are a number of tourism sites across the length and breadth of Ghana that can attract both domestic and inbound tourists. These include but not limited to the following:

- Tourist entertainment and recreation, including water parks such as, water sports, and etc.
- The development of a waterfront promenade in Accra.
- Key historical sites, including the Cape Coast and Elmina castles which contain the legacies of the of the Tran-Atlantic Slave Trade as well as the Kwame Nkrumah Memorial Park and Mausoleum, Manhyia Palace in Kumasi, the Ussher fort, James Town, Accra, Christiansburg Castle which served as the seat of government in the colonial times; Fort Metal Cross at Nfuma Dixcove, the Labaranga Mosque in the North, the Okomfo Anokye sword in Kumasi, Slave bathing site at Assin Manso and Assin Praso.
- Hotels and infrastructure of hotel resorts along Ghana's extensive coastline such as the Labadi Beach also known as La Pleasure Beach which is managed by the Labadi Beach Hotel and La Palm Royal Beach Hotel.
- Tourist facilities and infrastructure along Ghana's Volta delta and Volta Lake which is the largest artificial lake in the world.
- Ecotourism in Ghana's lush mountainous topography in Eastern and Volta Regions along Ghana's border with Togo, which features hiking, coffee plantations, and waterfalls. Notable among the mountains is the Afadjato Mountain which is the highest in the country. Ghana also can boast of the Wli Water fall which is tallest waterfall in West Africa, Kintampo, and Boti water falls.
- Ghana's national parks and wildlife reserves including The Kakum National Park. The Monkey Sanctuary, Mole National Park, Kumasi Zoological Gardens, Aburi Botanical Gardens, Butterfly sanctuary in the Ankasa Conservation Park, etc.

There are lots of other interesting locations that visitors might find it very great pleasure to visit as well, but have not been publicized to give them economic boost.

3.7 Tourism as major economic activity in Ghana

The tourism industry has contributed significantly to the Ghana's economy, particularly in recent times, the sector continues to demonstrate its potential as a key driver of growth. Between 2000 and 2005, tourists who visited Ghana increased by 46 per cent with spending rising to 68 per cent. According to a Bank of Ghana (2007), the industry was the third largest foreign exchange earner after merchandise exports and remittances from abroad. It is among the fastest growing and important sectors in the economy of the Ghana. Tourism receipts were then forecasted to reach \$1.5 billion by end 2007. Tourism remains a key economic driver in Ghana economy that which generates foreign exchange earnings, creates jobs and wealth and also stimulates other sectors of the economy. It is estimated that tourism yielded US\$2.2 million in 2015 with arrivals of 1.2 million. Currently Tourism is rated as the fourth largest source of foreign exchange earnings to the economy. Its contribution to the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is approximately 4.8%. The tourism industry in 2015 employed an estimated 393,000 people directly and indirectly from hotels, restaurants, travel trade, entertainment, recreational, tourist sites managers etc." (Ekow, 2022).

The Ghanaian Ministry of Tourism, Arts and Culture (MoTAC) projects that international tourism arrivals into Ghana in 2022 will increase to one million visitors. Hotels in the tourism sector in particular seeks to make recovery from the economic downturn meted by Covid by attracting international visitors to Ghana. Domestic tourist activity remains steady and account for about 800,000 visits annually. According to the International

Trade Administration (2022) “The MoTAC anticipates \$2.3 billion in revenue for the sector this year, up from \$2.1 billion in 2021 during the height of Covid travel disruptions and restrictions”.

3.8 Importance of using Graphic design in tourism development in Ghana

The aim of graphic design is to produce a piece of visual information for a target audience and thus stands for visual communication or communication design. The creative process in graphic design, however, involves the client and graphic designer. In order to create memorable design pieces, the designer uses different visual arts, images/illustrations, typography skills, and layout techniques. Organization of the various design elements in a graphic design is determined by the media such as posters, logos, package, website, etc. The field of graphic design, generally, comprises print, web, and broadcasting. Print designing consists of logos, packaging design, illustration & graphics, layout, etc.

In the modern competitive business environment, Graphic design plays a big role by creating impressive marketing materials such as brochures, business cards, websites, leaflets, stationeries and so on. Developing an impressive and memorable logo is a major requirement for any business if it is poised to build a brand identity. Similarly, businesses need the services of graphic designers to create unique mobile apps and social media pages for their business to thrive. This has made graphic design has become a part of doing business in the physical and virtual markets. Businesses continuously demand more graphic design items for them to communicate effectively with their audience.

In order to deal with the ever-increasing competition in the system, the adoption of graphic design strategies is eminent in drawing the attention of prospective customers towards the business. This assists entrepreneurs and business entities to communicate their message to the target audience effectively. For the tourism industry in Ghana to made strides, it is pertinent for them to see Graphic design as a crucial tool to be used to ensure that they communicate with prospective tourists and people in an efficient manner. Doing this will help deliver their message to the target audience in a very aesthetic way. Professionally created logo design for instance, assists in the making of a good and lasting impression on the prospective clients who will become loyal customers later. However, the first impression that a graphic design makes on the viewers is vital in drawing their attention towards a business.

3.9 Graphic Elements to be used to develop the Tourism Industry in Ghana

We living in a digital age that has given rise to several new types of graphic design. Emerging from the advancements in technology. Notable among them are:

- Website design that involves creating engaging and intuitive web pages for users. This includes overall layout, colour scheme and navigation.
- User experience (UX) design that focuses on ensuring a website or application is easy and satisfying to use. In this regard, designers emphasize on value, usability, adoptability and desirability.
- Motion graphics design or animation that brings visual elements to life through special effects, TV shows, video games and movies (Malvik, Rasmussen University, 2020).

First impression matters and so graphic design is used as a medium and an important tool to assist businesses to make positive and lasting impressions. This is so because the interaction a first-time visitor gets with any brand set the tone for the rest of the relationship. Normally, the first interaction comes in the form of the visual marketing materials which could be a poster, business card, a flyer, a new landing page on your website, a social media post, or even the product packaging. The Role of Design in the Tourism Industry is characterized by creating a brand, logo design and creative designs that bring the brand to life through visuals which truly engage the customers. “Design on flyers, brochures and photographic elements will support the success of the tourism industry” (Desamba, 2012).

A highlight on a beautiful design of a tourism destination will definitely keep people interested and imagine what they will see when they travel. Similarly, a beautiful island, animal sanctuary, attractive coastline etc., that

is not well known would be a major tourist destination if it is beautifully designed, and has appropriate branding strategy. It is surely a very profitable tool to employ in the tourism industry. Using print and visual media is an essential role to promote the tourism industry worldwide. As the old saying: "A picture is worth a thousand words". This is exactly what has prompted many tourism agencies and hotels to place designs as a top priority in growing their tourism industry (Desamba, 2012).

In the attempt to improve the tourism industry in Ghana, the industry players should work closely with various graphic design firms to help design corporate identities, brochures, websites and online promotions. It is an undeniable fact how important visually compelling messages are of concern to the travel sector and that graphic designs offer highly creative and fast turnaround on all projects. Graphic Design elements that have helped leading tourist countries and can be extremely relevant in the Ghana tourism industry include logos, brochures, websites, Social media such as YouTube, Facebook, WhatsApp, Banners, flyers, Motion graphics design, Infographics

Logos

Logos are essential elements of a brand and that it is important for the tourism industry in Ghana in general and the tourism sites in particular to ensure that the concept and content of their logos are purposeful and unique. What must be kept in mind in the design of logos is essentially the place where they operate from and the type of activity that pertain there because the requirement of a unique logo is very essential. The ability to communicate the idea of a perfect waterfall, beach holiday, safari, hiking, eco-tourism, etc., to the prospective customers is the sole responsibility of the individual entities. For that reason, as Darwin (2020) puts it, you have to be very thoughtful as everything depends on how effectively you are able to portray it through your logo design. A well designed and well-liked logos can constantly influence the decision to visit a place than logos that are less well-liked. The logo therefore has to be distinct and a memorable one. A good logo is likely to build goodwill for the Ghanaian tourism market as other businesses have achieved greater recognition with their logos. Indeed, with a logo design that has a good aesthetic value and design elements that appeal to the senses, the viewers will gain confidence and have faith in the industry's products or services. An attractive logo design will help win customers and many of them will gradually become loyal to your business.

Brochures

Tourism is an information intensive business and with technological advances, the way in which information is stored, managed and transmitted to potential visitors has been transformed. Notwithstanding the extensive use of Internet technologies in tourism marketing, information is still predominantly disseminated through printed brochures and this has maintained and unaffected by personalization trends (Migas, Anastasiadou, & Stirling, 2008) .

Hiippalla (2013) in Moldovan & Moldovan (2015) states that Tourist brochures are a form of print media advertising which are part of the pre-travel materials intended to inform, convince, lure and eventually sell tourist packages". Again, Moldovan & Moldovan quoted Andereck (2005) by saying, "Brochures help travelers to make informed decisions and the tour operators to better promote their packages". Indisputably, printed brochures are said to increase awareness of local products, services and attractions. A research according to Visitor International (2022) revealed that the travel plans of 95% of visitors, who picked up a brochure during a visit at their destination, were influenced by them. During their trip, a brochure, map or travel guide served as the most important source of information for the visitors. It pointed out that 2 out of every 3 visitors representing 67% picked up brochures during their visit. This influenced the actions of 95% of them. Printed brochures are powerful influencers of visitors' behavior. It is clear that in this increasingly digital world, brochures have a major effect on visitors' plans and actions, especially, in the moment, on location, and during their trip".

Pamphlets and brochures are also a good marketing tool for a spot of tourism. Professionally designed brochures and pamphlets that are attractive and eye catching can make the tourism sites appear more attractive than they

really are. For example, it is the very attractive brochure design of Sentosa Island in Singapore and that of Disneyland in Hong Kong that makes the places look more beautiful and attract people to visit it and that role of graphic design is very influential on the tourism industry (Desamba, 2012). Indeed, a glossy brochure that pleases the eye is a satisfyingly fun.

Responsive websites

With the understanding of the ever-increasing importance of responsive website design, advanced travel and tourism operators employ the service of graphic designers to develop sites to assist them in content management. Such an excellent platform or sites are thoroughly tested to ensure that they look great and function correctly across desktop, tablet and mobile devices (Mercer Design, 2022). Internet marketing for tourism products provides a great opportunity to announce to a wide range of people what is to on offer so as to realize the power of online marketing. Even though traditional marketing is quite similar in so many ways, the rate of exposure offered by Internet marketing for tourism products provides a higher rate of exposure and visibility of the company becomes higher. The wide coverage of the Internet world provides that tourism agencies and offices the platform for them to advertise possible destinations, packages, tours and other large amount of information. The immensity and accessibility of the internet cannot be overemphasized.

Internet marketing for Ghanaian tourism industry products will improve the positioning of their products and also make them more accessible. Using Tourism Internet to market the products of the sites will, help them know more about the customers by giving them a better way to communicate with them when it is strategically thought-out and developed, in this case the commercial goals will as come alive (F.WC, 2022). In support of this, the F.WC (2022) declares that even though almost every industry needs to take advantage of internet resources nowadays, it would not be out of place to say that the tourism industry is the one that does needs it most. This is so because tourism industry is a fast-paced business which does frequent product updates and last-minute ads. Therefore, it is good, almost a MUST for this industry to have a functional and client website design.

According to Desamba (2012), the tourism industry is currently benefited greatly from the design to the rise of the internet which makes it possible for every city, country and state has their own website. It is on this site that they can display the best things that will encourage tourists to come and visit. Desamba maintains that the Internet is a powerful marketing tool in the tourism industry and have quite a dramatic effect on the tourism industry itself. For this reason, a good web design is required to make the promotion of the tourist spot very important and interesting. The design of the tourism sites should be one that features the best things that can be enjoyed by tourists and motivate their desire to visit the place which ultimately has the advantage for the tourism industry (Desamba, 2012).

Information Technology plays an important role in the hospitality and tourism industry today. It also helps in the reduction of costs, enhances operational efficiency, and improves services and customer experience as well. With technology, customers and businesses benefit from improved communication systems, reservations, and guest services. The use of technology makes it possible the tourism industries to substitute expensive human labour with technological labour thereby reducing labour costs also helps to eliminate customer service issues. (Entre, 2018).

Billboards

Billboards are big outdoor advertising structures that can be likened to an oversized poster. Businesses use billboards to promote their brand, offer, or campaign by displaying advertisements. They are normally erected in areas that have high-traffic such as along highways or near shopping malls to provoke the attention of the highest number of drivers and pedestrians. It is an effective marketing strategy used in getting a greater number of viewers and long-term brand impressions. Additionally, it creates strong branding with the use of huge text sizes, images of celebrities with noticeable features and benefits of the products, and other important

information. Inferring from Mishra (2022), four types of Billboards including digital billboard, mobile billboard, static billboards as well as three dimensional billboards can be used by the tourism companies in Ghana to advertise their brand and products. The use of digital billboard will enable the tourism companies to generate with the computer systems and software to display assorted images and text. The display can be made to show running text, or can be changed depending on the time of day. The ever-changing texts will create the maximum impact and reach for the target audiences.

Using mobile billboard is simply branding the sites or products on buses, cars, and other moving vehicles. In so doing, it is more likely for the target audience to notice it. In this regard, as the vehicle moves around the area, the company is being promoted as long as it moves from one place to the other. Static billboards are the large printed vinyl stretched across the surface of billboard. In this case, individual elements in the billboard cannot be changed in a matter of seconds or minutes instead, it has to be re-erected and fastened to the structure. Modern advertisers have resorted to the use of three-dimensional billboards to capture the viewers' attention and curiosity. This is done by using three-dimensional dramatic visuals and pop-up book style graphics. Sometimes, static images can transform into a moving object that can display different messages at different times. These modes of advertising technology can be adopted to make the tourism sites and their products visible.

Banner Ads

A banner ad is a form of advertising that Ghanaian tourism operators can adopt to use online. Looking at the amount of time most people spend out online each day, it is no gainsaying to point out that this is where business-minded tourism entities in Ghana should focus more attention to catch the eyes of the global market. Even though Banner ads are small advertisements on Web sites, they go a long way to attract the targeted audience and build brand awareness. To achieve success with this form of advertising, is to determine the information including the logo and a memorable name in the ads so potential customers can remember. Banner adverts can conveniently be placed on the front page of a tourism website to arouse interest. In this regard, a good and attractive design becomes imperative in order to create a delightful impression on a tourist destination. Things that sell from a resort are beautiful and interesting things in place and the role of graphic design in the tourism industry is to highlight the beauty, uniqueness and create the potential for an increased traffic.

Social media advertising in tourism

In recent times, Mobile tablets and smartphones have taken over from the use of large desktop computers which has made them virtually nonexistent. This is helpful in tourism, because a lot of the travellers take some type of mobile device along with them during a trip. With this mobile technology, the hospitality and tourism businesses are able to make the necessary provisions as regards their customers' advised of change and delays to their reservations, offer deals, and also advertise by way of GPS tracking (Entre, 2018). The use of social media has become the order of the day and that if the tourism industry in Ghana desires to develop, it has to be abreast with the technology that social media uses in promoting business.

Social media enables especially young people to share the most significant memories comprising the posting of photographs, motion graphics of events, and scenery from their travels with a vast audience through YouTube, Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram, Tweeter, etc. Tourism companies in Ghana should know that this is a more powerful way of attracting new travellers than simple advertisements and encourage people to share their real experiences online. Currently many people find the Social media on tourism as an avenue to research on the possible places of visit before embarking on a trip and its use transforms the decision making of people. More so, social media encouraged tourists to share their travel experiences with other people which, in turn help the people to gain confidence and trust in the tourism agencies.

Infographics in Tourism

Infographics are a great way that summarizes information that an audience would have skimmed over or skip reading completely. del Rosario (2022) admonishes that "Studies show that infographics, which combine visuals

with text are three times more engaging than text-only content because humans are heavily influenced by visuals and that, adding relevant graphics to text can deepen our understanding and recollection of complex information”.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Graphic design has played and continues to play pivotal roles in the development of tourism in Countries across the world who have been recognized as leading tourism destinations where tourists crave to visit and spend time away from home.
2. The tourism industry as a business entity, requires graphic designs to convey their messages clearly. For this reason, the industry must employ the services of Graphic designers because they are trained professionals who understand the “technique to persuade, engage, and entertain audience using various visual elements”.
3. Graphic designs serve as great tools which the tourism industry players can use to earn trust and goodwill in their market.
4. Graphic design does not only make thing look good but it organizes information to assist in delivering a message in the most impactful way possible. When the tourism companies are are able to combine the right images and a well-written banner/headline, executed professionally by a graphic designer in a well-established package, then their message will hit their target.
5. A well Designed and creative branding on the tourism industry has the potential to inspire people to make a trip to some tourist attractions. This is so because a successful tourism branding and attractive designing will make a tourist spot become famous in the public eye.
6. The tourism companies and operators should note that beauty is attractive and graphic design brings about the beauty they require to attract the target audience and the prospective visitors. A well-designed marketing piece helps the audience see the appealing graphics to reel them in the advertising message.
7. A good and eye-catching Billboards designs billboard may make a prospect stop and view it intentionally or unintentionally. Unlike forms of advertising, billboards help to ensure brand exposure and brand recall and also appeal to all ages whether adults or children.
8. Using powerful and elegant logos, banners, interactive website, internet and social media advertising is one of the best things any company can do and so the tourism sites in Ghana should adopt them to register their name and brand out there. They will find it as a worthy investment that will make them realize their goals if they money into it. The more people know about the existence of the sites, the more customers you will draw in leading to more income generation.

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